

AIES-ZOO

Basic specifications for the automated pipeline for the data download, process and EcoPart/EcoTaxa upload.

1) Download data from UVP6

Stop acquisition to download, then reboot → Protocol from Octos from Fabio WISIP (also in UVP App).

2) Prepare data for EcoPart/EcoTaxa

a) Metadata, Samples, Split into two projects (UV light on/off) → Python code from Flavien and Joelle

b) Process particles → Move and rename files

c) Process images → Code C for segmentation from Laurent N + TSV generation

3) Import into EcoPart/EcoTaxa

Import data into FTP (via code), then call EcoPart API for successive import into EcoPart then EcoTaxa.

The logo consists of the word "APP" in a blue, sans-serif font, centered within a light gray oval that has a thin blue border.

APP

- There could be more than one UVP plugged. -> run as many app as instruments
- Python app
- Running into a dk container for more systems compatibility and portability
- No UI only .env containing configurations
- Should be at least sftp not ftp.

Code to collect or create :

- Protocol from octos Fabio WISIP
- Python code from Flavien and Joelle for Metadata, Samples, Split into two projects
- Move and rename files for particules ?
- Code C for segmentation from Laurent N
- TSV generation ?
- Import to ftp Julie to create
- Import to ecopart and ecotaxa Julie to create

Sur ce git il y a les 2 scripts qui nous permettent d'assembler les séquences UVP en séquences de 24h (uvp6_time_merge) et l'autre de créer les samples correspondant (uvp6_create_meta)

https://github.com/ecotaxa/UVP_toolboxpy

Ancien et nouveau format des lignes d'entrée :

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Jd4QcQ4EzbPPL9FOeq8KZcmVLgHcnR0?usp=drive_link

Protocol octos :

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Fbof1KYZnDB6SeyVDBnfaVROwMIIDIIOU?usp=drive_link

ici : [uvp6_missions:\uvp6_sn000238lp](#)

Projet aneris de tortilla de vilanova sur lequel on fait le pipeline à la mains

Le document décrivant notre pipeline manuel :

[uvp_dvlpt:_UVP6_new\Integration\Observatoires_cables\EMSO_OBSSEA_SMARTBAY\data_pipeline\20240702_aneris_handmade_data-pipeline.docx](#)

Code C de LN :

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/11iQYXTTau0voK98hxFOw72s0poE-KNfy?usp=drive_link